

BIM FOR INFORMATION MANAGEMENT IN STRUCTURAL SAFETY CONTROL OF EMBANKMENT DAMS

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Supervisors

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Abstract

The application of Building Information Modelling (BIM) for the integration of large volumes of information and data analysis is a current practice, and increasingly frequent, in the civil construction sector. However, the application of the BIM methodology in infrastructure works, such as in the case of dams, is still not a widespread practice, especially in embankment dams.

Dams' construction is essential for different uses, such as water supply, energy generation, mining exploration. A large part of these dams is built with compacted soil and have specific structures that ensure flow control, stability and compatibility of deformations. Notwithstanding the social, economic and environmental impacts generated by possible failures of these structures are of greater importance and relevance for the community, and, unfortunately, have been occurring. The efforts that can be made to control the safety of a dam are always essential. The safety control of a dam is carried out through visual inspections and analysis of the instrumentation measurement. In some dams, instrumentation measurements are still carried out manually, without processes integrating the information. As a result, the use of BIM models integrated with a database, and specific tools for data analysis, becomes an interesting procedure for the solution and resolution of some problems arising from the dam safety analysis process.

The use of the BIM methodology in embankment dams with a focus on the analysis of dam safety is the main objective of this work. The procedures developed in this dissertation in partnership with the Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (LNEC) aim to establish the connection between different existing information in order to generate a BIM model, for three-dimensional visualization of the data obtained from the placed instrumentation. Furthermore, the connection between the database (SQLite) and a data analysis tool (Power BI) is also established, the

methodology being tested for a type of instrument (settlement batteries), allowing the establishment of the connection and data integration between the BIM model, the database and the data analysis tool. The developed application allowed us to conclude that the use of the BIM methodology for information analysis is very promising, there are, however, several challenges for the generalized implementation of a solution.

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/2021-AlineHeleno-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/rbmfiF9lg1k>

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